

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL FOR IMPROVED USER EXPERIENCE ON E-LEARNING PLATFORMS.

Onwe, Festus Chijioke,

Open, Distance and e-Learning Centre,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
Phone no: 2348067980358,
Email: festus.onwe@uniport.edu.ng

Alo, Uzoma Rita

Department of Computer Science/ Informatics,
Alex- Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu-Alike.
2347034477250
alo.uzoma@funai.edu.ng

Abstract:

Online Education and the use of learning management platforms have become very popular and effective in offering distance learning. Admit the feat achieved, learning systems still struggles to dynamically modify appropriate teaching strategies in response to the shifting attitudes and behaviors of the learner, as it is possible in the traditional face to face teaching, where the tutor can easily adjust on noticing changes in the reactions of the learners. In this study, we sought for solution that could enhance the experience of users on the learning management platforms, which have led to the development of a model called MultiNetEmotion, a conceptual ensemble learning architecture integrating ResNet, VGGFace2, and custom CNN models, which have been trained to detect in real-time facial expression and classify the emotions of a learner as either angry, fear, happy, neutral, sad, and surprise and therefore make recommendations to the learners. The dataset used for the training was extracted from Kaggle, the training and validation was done and the accuracy improve initially, demonstrating that the model successfully learned the features of the training data. However, after around the third epoch, a divergence between the training and validation accuracies becomes apparent. The training accuracy continues to increase steadily, reaching about 87% by the final epoch, indicating that the model fits well to the training data. On the other hand, the validation accuracy experiences a plateau, with minor fluctuations around 60% from the third epoch onward.

Keywords — Convolution Neural Network, Distant Education, Facial Expression, Machine Learning

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

This Every aspect of society and human endeavours have continued to pay attention to new technologies, and mobile and internet of things devices are contributing to greater internet connectivity in the modern world than ever before. [1] Digital technology being an integral part of educational services, providing easy access to learning, enabling and enhancing the pedagogy [2] has led to a number of formal and informal learning environments that differ from traditional learning environments in terms of form, function, features, and patterns. They provide students flexible and easy access to education, allowing them to pick up new skills and information [3].

The past decade have witnessed a geometric increase in online education (e-Learning) from 1,602,970 to 6,714,792 students completing at least one online course [4]. This has shown that massive open online courses have increased its availability and reach of learners. [5] in their research predicts that in 2026, e-learning will reach almost 400billion dollars in the globe. As of 2021, 15 universities in Nigeria were providing online education; 11 of these were federal, two were state-run, and the remaining two were private. The only single-mode university in Nigeria was the federal National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) with 640,942 enrolled students spread across 90 study centers and 15 correctional centers, it was also the largest university in West Africa in terms of student population [6].

Due to the enormous expansion of online education, free or paid online courses are now offered via Technology Enhanced Learning Environments (TELE) [7]. Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL), often known as Online Education, e-Learning, or Distance Learning, has drastically changed how people study and teach [8].

According to [9] e-learning is widely recognized as an educational method that enables the adaptable dissemination of knowledge and abilities to multiple recipients at various locations and times. Students can be active learners when they have the freedom to select their own study materials and set their own schedules for time, place, and pace. For e-learning to be effective, interactive, which is an interesting element of a successful e-learning, and interactivity makes learning interesting and effective by making it possible for both the tutor and the students contribute to the learning, which could be described as bi-directional learning. This interactivity is achieved through active engagement of the students with the system. There are majorly two factors, which could have effects on the results of e-learning. They include (1) Views of learners regarding online education and (2) The information technology that makes e-learning possible [10]. The Users' experiences and opinions of these systems have a significant impact on how well e-learning works.

The learners can interact with learning environments in two ways. The first involves the mental response to test questions and secondly, their emotional response gotten through facial expression [11]. It is a primary knowledge that most of human interaction with computer software involves non-verbal communication; researchers have focused on the user's emotional state on their researches [12]. Research have also shown that

human face is one of the most important ways of measuring student's engagement and recognizing their emotions during learning [13]. Although various features can be used for emotion recognition, including facial expression, voice, EEG, and text, [14] noted that the eyes, nose, eyebrows are primary means of expressing emotions, other features like forehead, ears, might be excluded in further analysis. Facial expressions are most prominent in trying to examine the learner's emotions for a good number of reasons such as including the fact that they are visible, have many features that are helpful for recognizing emotions, and are simpler to gather a sizable dataset of faces than other methods of human recognition [15]. Facial expression is a naturally and universally way for humans to express their emotions. It is among the most effective nonverbal communication channels and contains a wealth of useful information. E-learning may benefit from the ability to recognize facial expressions that convey students' feelings and relay them back to the instructor.

[16] opined that the inability to absorb and assimilate knowledge during learning might eventually cause a learner to become perplexed, feel strained (unable to comprehend), and feel bored and tired (lose interest and attention). This could lead to behavioral changes in the learner, such as confusion, frustration, depression, gloom, or anger, which could eventually lead to skipping or abandoning learning sessions. Thus, a learner's unstable and depressed emotions result in a low or unpleasant sensation, which impairs learning performance [17]. Positive feelings like happiness, neutrality, and surprise can be attributed to students who pay attention in class, but negative emotions like sadness, disgust, anger, and boredom can be attributed to students who are not paying attention [18]. These emotions of happiness, which stands for contentment and enthusiasm, anxiety, which represents insecurity, sorrow, which indicates discouragement, and anger, which expresses annoyance or aggravation shown characterize how students feel when utilizing the learning management system [16].

Machine learning is revolutionizing education and radically altering research, teaching, and learning. It is a new method of speeding up advancement in the educational system. One of the best examples of how technology enhances human processes is machine learning in education, particularly in the areas of teaching and learning. Educators are using Machine learning to spot struggling students earlier and take action to improve success and retention.

Convolutional neural networks (CCNs) is a type of machine learning model, and a special type of deep learning algorithm that is designed for task that requires object recognition, image classification, detection and segmentation [19]. Learning enormous volumes of data is one of the advantages of deep learning [20].

The aim of this study was to develop MultiNetEmotion model a novel conceptual ensemble learning architecture integrating ResNet, VGG16, and custom CNN, which will detect in real-time facial expressions and classify the emotions of learners surprise, anger, happiness, sadness, neutral, and fear and therefore make recommendations to the learners. The specific objectives will include to:

1. To develop a robust emotion detection model (MultiNetEmotion) capable of recognising six human emotions, surprise, anger, joy, neutral, fear, happiness with accuracy.
2. Train the dataset and also test the models ability to detect facial expressions and emotions.
3. To leverage transfer learning architecture, ResNet50 and VGG16 and create a hybrid model for effective feature extraction.
4. To enable real-time emotion detection using live camera feeds for seamless integration into interactive e-learning platforms.

The development of MultiNetEmotion contributes to societal advancement by leveraging artificial intelligence to address emotional well-being, a vital aspect often overlooked in digital education systems by incorporating emotional intelligence into technology. The project promotes inclusivity, catering to the diverse emotional landscapes of learners. This initiative aligns with global efforts to improve mental health and reduce the psychological barriers to education, particularly in remote or underserved areas where e-learning platforms are a primary educational resource. Its emphasis on personalized content recommendations paves the way for more empathetic human-machine interactions. This will extend beyond e-learning into sectors such as healthcare, customer service, and entertainment. MultiNetEmotion will enhance the learning experience by recognizing and responding to emotional cues, ultimately leading to more engaging, supportive, and productive educational environments. Simultaneously, it underscores the importance of emotional intelligence in technological innovations, fostering a society where AI solutions actively contribute to emotional and mental well-being.

2 RELATED RESEARCH

We briefly undertake to review existing scholarly works, research articles that are relevant to this study. We provided a comprehensive understanding of the current state of knowledge on the topic, identified gaps or inconsistencies in the literatures, and highlight the most significant findings and trend.

[23] did a study that proposed an intelligent educational recommender model for web-based learning environments that, depending on the profile of the learner, can offer meaningful recommendations for the most engaging and pertinent learning resources. It chooses educational resources that are suitable for students. Online learners' conduct is easily observable, highly expressive, and indicative of their individual characteristics. The model used was based on learner's interests and a semantic analysis of the course materials. They used naive Bays Classifier and K-Means Clustering machine learning algorithm implementation, and the dataset used was a primary data generated from the user survey they carried out, using a google form. They

obtained 80% accuracy with the Naïve Bays classifier algorithm and 91% accuracy with K-means algorithm. It was observed that, the testing time for K-Means is much more than that of NB model. This is due to the inherent characteristics of K-Means algorithm, which is known as a lazy learner as compare to NB.

[12] used Real-Time Emotional Analysis and Assessment to study User Experience in E-Learning. In order to better understand the emotional reactions during user-platform interaction, he conducted an experiment with 23 university students, comparing the efficacy of a retrospective questionnaire called Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) with a real-time face and eye detection framework (MIORA). In order to track students' emotional responses and assess consistency, usability problems were purposefully added to the system. The results of the SAM questionnaire demonstrated that participants tended to express the most prominent emotions they felt, even though less intense emotions were not always reported. Certain emotions confused the participants, as was evident in the final task, where the MIORA identified dread while the SAM questionnaire indicated anxiety. Emoj's dataset and questionnaire served as the main sources of information. [24] proposed an end-to-end deep learning framework based on attentional convolutional network to classify the underlying emotion in the face images. In their research, they focused on the important part of the face using visualization technique to detect different emotions. They used a secondary data which include FER-2013, Ck+, FERG and JAFFE and achieved an accuracy of 70.02%.

A related study on the use of attentional convolutional networks for facial expression recognition was conducted by [25]. On a range of datasets, they offer a deep learning technique based on attentional convolutional networks that performs better than previous models. This time, they obtained the following accuracy using datasets from CK+, FERG, JAFFE, and FER-2013 separately. The Fer-2013 dataset, which is more difficult than other facial expression recognition datasets, had an accuracy of 70.02 percent; the FERG dataset had an accuracy of 99.3 percent; the JAFFE dataset had an accuracy of 92.8 percent; and CK+ provided a range of accuracy levels from 91.4 percent to 98.0 percent.

[26] worked on Human Facial Emotion Recognition using Deep Neural Networks, the model used data augmentation technique for data preprocessing. They used secondary dataset CK+ and JAFFE. The model classified emotion classes and made it efficient for real world applications. They got accuracy of 96.91% for JAFFE and 98.49% for

A study on facial emotion detection to gauge learners' mental states in an online learning environment was conducted by [13]. Confusion, dissatisfaction, satisfaction, and frustration are the four complex emotions they identified. They also demonstrated that evaluating an emotion based on a single image capture is insufficient to gauge a learner's mental state. Using the FER 2013 dataset, they applied a CNN model and achieved a 65 percent accuracy rate.

[27] used bidirectional LSTM-CNN to construct a facial expression recognition model. To enhance the performance of models from their earlier work, they employed a deep learning architecture, which automatically extracts features for image analysis and classification. The BiLSTM-CNN model's maximum

accuracy was 99.43 percent after augmentation and 81.82 percent prior to augmentation. With an accuracy of 69–70 percent prior to augmentation and a notable increase to 98–57 percent following augmentation, the LSTM-CNN model had the second-highest accuracy. In order to enhance the models' performance, they attempted to augment images in the CK+ dataset and compared built CNN, LSTM-CNN, and BiLSTM-CNN models. With a value of 99.43 percent, the BiLSTM-CNN Model with data augmentation thus attains the highest accuracy. This suggests that data augmentation addresses the overfitting scenario and enhances the trained model's performance.

[14] researched on facial expression recognition, they proposed an algorithm with the combination of Local Binary Patterns (LBP) and oriented FAST and rotated BRIEF (ORB) features extracted from facial expression. They used a secondary dataset from JAFFE, CK+ and MMI facial expression database and SVM classification was performed for the facial classification. They got 84.6 % accuracy.

A study by [28] examined the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in identifying and assessing classroom teaching behavior. The SVM's linear separable initial is used to obtain the classroom teaching behavior characteristic data, and the relationship between the characteristic sample data and the hyperplane is ascertained. They researched the identification of instructional behavior in the classroom and put forth a brand-new approach built on the convolutional neural network (CNN). Using the SVM linear separable initial, we first determine the relationship between the characteristic sample data in the hyperplane, then we obtain the heterogeneous support vector of the online learning behavior characteristic sample data in the SVM hyperplane, and finally we complete the characteristic data extraction. They created the confusion matrix to determine the weight of the indicators of classroom teaching behavior, verify their consistency, and complete the evaluation of the classroom teaching behavior. Convolution, pooling, and fully connected layers are used to identify classroom teaching behavior through an analytical hierarchy process.

[29] Introduced an embedded system that offers a complete solution for identifying driving fatigue. It uses an AD8232 heart rate module, an Arduino Uno, a Nvidia Jetson Nano developer kit, and computer vision and deep learning techniques. The system was able to monitor the driver's condition in real time, assess it to spot any indications of fatigue, and respond accordingly. The onboard camera module continuously monitors the driver. In order to verify the Nvidia Jetson Nano scenario, the core system retrieves and analyzes the frames using computer vision and deep learning techniques. Eye and mouth localization techniques are used to identify the driver's states from 68 different facial landmarks. To categorize the states, experimentally driven threshold data was used. Any variation in heart rate associated with drowsiness is detected by the onboard heart rate module, which continuously measures heart rates. In order to handle the pandemic situation, this system added additional face mask detection using a deep learning framework based on convolutional neural networks. To guarantee continuous detection, the heart rate module operates in parallel while the other modules operate conditionally sequentially. In real time, it identified any indication of sleepiness and triggered

the alarm. With 97point 44 percent accuracy in fatigue detection and 97point 90 percent accuracy in face mask identification, the system passed the first round of laboratory testing as well as some real-world experiments. [30] created a model that uses a convolutional neural network (CNN) to measure a driver's level of fatigue based on changes in their eye movements. This can help reduce the number of accidents caused by sleepy driving and increase road safety. We used CNN and VGG16 models to identify and classify tired facial expressions into four groups: open, closed, yawning, and no yawning. Subsequently, the models were evaluated on a dataset comprising 2900 images of eye conditions associated with driver fatigue, encompassing various factors such as age, gender, head position, and lighting. The results of the devolved models show high accountability, while the CNN model received accuracy rates of 97 percent, precision of 99 percent, recall, and F-score values of 99 percent. Seventy-four percent of the VGG16 model was accurate.

[31] study examined how well people with ASD could emote on their faces in response to spoken cues. Using the Janssen Autism Knowledge Engine (JAKE), they measured the facial expressions of 144 people with ASD (n = 144) and 41 members of the normally developing (TD) control group using automated facial expression analysis software (FACET). ASD and TD groups differed in their capacity to make facial expressions, as evidenced by the activation of facial action units that represent pleased, afraid, astonished, disgusted, but not angry or sad emotions. Parent-reported social communication abilities were linked with facial action unit activation.

Boz & Kose 2018 designed an Artificial Intelligence based system for extracting emotions from facial expressions. A Cascade Feed-forward Artificial Neural Network model, trained by the Vortex Optimization Algorithm, a new optimization technique, makes up the system. Several emotion extraction system settings were applied to various photo data sets from the literature in order to conduct the investigation. Upon evaluation, the system showed the capacity to discern various emotions from images pertaining to people of different racial and gender identities. Additionally, it has been observed that the extraction performance of an intelligent system might be impacted by a combination of data from other sets. The study's conclusions also inspired the writers to organize further research projects in the future using the methodology they had used. To test if extraction performance can be increased, it is first intended to adjust the parameters for the preset number of points over the face, the size of the shot, and any other alternative conditions. However, in order to determine whether extra data can still have an impact on the system's performance, other alternative data sets will also be used using the same configurations as the previously mentioned approach. In conclusion, as it is evident from the justifications given beneath the earlier sections for the software system developed for tracking data, the system will be applied for live or recorded videos.

METHODOLOGY

In this research a MultiNetEmotion framework, conceptual ensemble learning architecture integrating ResNet, VGG16, and custom CNN, which will detect in real-time facial expressions and classify the emotions of learners as either surprise, anger, happiness, sadness, neutral, and fear and therefore make recommendations

to the learners will be developed. The model will aim to bridge the gap identified during the literature review. Adopted methodology for both information gathering and system development will be presented. Detailed analysis of the existing and the new system with their strength and weaknesses will be explained.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology introduces the research design, which combines supervised learning and ensemble techniques using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Specifically ResNet, VGG16, and a custom CNN architecture. It describes the data collection process, including the datasets used for training, validation, and testing. This is followed by the preprocessing steps applied to the dataset, such as image augmentation, resizing, and normalization, to prepare the data for optimal model performance. Subsequently, we delved into the architecture of the proposed MultiNetEmotion model, explaining how the ResNet and VGG16 models are used for feature extraction, while the CNN is employed for final emotion classification. Transfer learning techniques are also explored, highlighting how pre-trained models were fine-tuned to improve performance on the emotion detection task. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the training procedure.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The dataset used for training, evaluating and validation of MultiNetEmotion model was obtained from Kaggle. This dataset was specifically curated for facial emotion recognition tasks and comprises images categorized into six distinct facial expressions: surprise, anger, happiness, sadness, neutral, and fear.

The dataset is organized into two (2) for the purpose of training and testing. Each set contains a subsets corresponding to the different emotional expressions, allowing for an intuitive structure that facilitates efficient model configuration and training. The Training Set includes a total of 28,079 grayscale images, each with a resolution of 48x48 pixels. These images are cropped and aligned to ensure that the face is centrally positioned and occupies a consistent portion of each image. The Testing Set consists of 7,178 images with the same dimensions and pre-processing applied as in the training set, ensuring consistency across both sets and enabling an accurate evaluation of the model's performance.

THE SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

The MultiNetEmotion Framework was built on a multi-phase architecture that integrates real-time facial detection, emotion recognition, and adaptive recommendations based on the user's detected emotional state. The system employs a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model trained on a diverse dataset of facial expressions to predict six distinct emotion categories: anger, fear, happiness, neutral, sadness, and surprise.

In the MultinetEmotion framework, once the student login to study, the following processes are initiated;

- a) Image Acquisition which captures live video input using a camera or extracts static images for emotion detection.

- b) Preprocesses the images by resizing, normalizing, and converting them into a format suitable for the model. This step includes transforming color images into grayscale or retaining RGB channels depending on model configuration.
- c) Feature Extraction and Classification which utilizes a CNN model to analyze facial features and predict the corresponding emotion class based on the input image.
- d) Real-Time Emotion Monitoring which captures the user's emotion over a period (e.g., 10 minutes), providing continuous feedback on the emotional state.
- e) Emotion-Based Recommendation when the predefined time window capture, MultiNetEmotion evaluates the user's overall emotional state and offers recommendations. If the system detects positive emotions such as Happy or Neutral, it suggests the user continue with their current activity. If negative emotions such as
- f) Sad, Angry, or Fear are detected, the system recommends a more uplifting activity, such as watching comic or cartoon videos to improve mood.

The diagram below shows the system flow of the MultiNetEmotion framework

MODEL PARAMETERS

This section presents a detailed analysis of the model parameters used in the proposed MultiNetEmotion framework, explaining the architecture, connections between different layers, and the number of trainable and non-trainable parameters in the system. Understanding these parameters is essential for evaluating the model's computational complexity, memory requirements, and overall efficiency. The model comprises several layers, including convolutional layers, fully connected layers, and dropout layers, which collectively contribute to the system's capability to perform robust emotion classification.

The input layer serves as the entry point for image data into the model. It accepts images with a shape of $48 \times 48 \times 348 \times 48 \times 3$, corresponding to grayscale images with three color channels (RGB). While these images are processed as grayscale, the three channels ensure compatibility with networks that expect coloured images. This layer does not contain any parameters, as its purpose is solely to structure the input data. Its output Shape is (None,48,48,3) (None,48,48,3).

Figure 1: Multinet Emotion Framework

The ResNet50 model, a well-known deep convolutional neural network, forms a critical component of the MultiNetEmotion architecture. This network is primarily composed of residual blocks, which enable deeper networks by addressing the vanishing gradient problem through identity mapping. ResNet50 has been pre-trained on large-scale datasets and is used here to extract high-level features from the input images. It has an output of (None,2,2,2048) (None,2,2,2048) and Parameters of 23,587,712. The ResNet50 layer connects to the input layer and processes the input images to produce a 2x2 feature map with 2048 channels, representing complex features extracted from the image.

In addition to ResNet50, the MultiNetEmotion framework includes the VGG16 model, another powerful convolutional neural network known for its simplicity and depth. It has an Output Shape: (None,1,1,512)(None,1,1,512) and parameters of 14,714,688. This layer connects to the same input as the ResNet50 model and generates a smaller 1x1 feature map with 512 channels. These features capture different aspects of the input image, complementing the features extracted by ResNet50.

The two flattening layers are applied to the outputs of the ResNet50 and VGG16 models, transforming the multidimensional feature maps into one-dimensional vectors. These vectors can then be processed by fully connected layers for final classification. Flattening these outputs reduces the dimensional complexity of the feature maps while retaining the important extracted features for classification.

Moreover, the concatenation layer combines the flattened outputs from both the ResNet50 and VGG16 models. By merging these feature vectors, the model can utilize the strengths of both networks, enhancing the overall performance of the MultiNetEmotion framework. The concatenate layer ensures that the network can integrate high-level features (from ResNet50) and mid-level features (from VGG16) for more nuanced emotion classification.

Additional fully connected (dense) layers play a vital role in the final stages of classification, translating the concatenated feature vector into a prediction for one of the six emotion categories. There are several dense layers with progressively fewer neurons, each followed by dropout layers to prevent overfitting with five dense Layer each with different input and output parameters. The dense layers apply learned weights to the concatenated feature vector, ultimately producing a six-dimensional output corresponding to the six emotion classes in the dataset (Angry, Fear, Happy, Neutral, Sad, Surprise).

Lastly, dropout layers are introduced between the dense layers to mitigate overfitting by randomly setting a fraction of the input units to zero during training. This regularization technique helps ensure that the model generalizes well to unseen data, improving robustness.

The total number of parameters in the MultiNetEmotion model is 42,924,358, comprising both trainable and non-trainable parameters. Of these, 42,871,238 are trainable, while 53,120 are non-trainable. The model size is approximately 163.74 MB, and it includes pre-trained components (ResNet50 and VGG16), which allow the system to leverage learned features from large-scale datasets, thus accelerating convergence and enhancing accuracy. By combining the strengths of ResNet50 and VGG16 through a hybrid architecture, and incorporating fully connected and dropout layers, the MultiNetEmotion model is well-positioned to efficiently detect and classify emotions from facial images in real-time environments. The use of pre-trained models not only reduces the need for extensive training but also ensures that the system can extract meaningful features from complex image data. The overall structure balances computational efficiency and model complexity, making it suitable for deployment in real-time applications such as emotion recognition in educational or interactive settings.

Model: "functional"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #	Connected to
input_layer (InputLayer)	(None, 48, 48, 3)	0	-
resnet50 (Functional)	(None, 2, 2, 2048)	23,587,712	input_layer[0][0]
vgg16 (Functional)	(None, 1, 1, 512)	14,714,688	input_layer[0][0]
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 8192)	0	resnet50[0][0]
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 512)	0	vgg16[0][0]
concatenate (Concatenate)	(None, 8704)	0	flatten[0][0], flatten_1[0][0]
dense (Dense)	(None, 512)	4,456,960	concatenate[0][0]
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 512)	0	dense[0][0]
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 256)	131,328	dropout[0][0]
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 256)	0	dense_1[0][0]
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 128)	32,896	dropout_1[0][0]
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 6)	774	dense_2[0][0]

Total params: 42,924,358 (163.74 MB)

Trainable params: 42,871,238 (163.54 MB)

Non-trainable params: 53,120 (207.50 KB)

Fig. 2: Multi Net Emotion model

NOVELTY OF THE ARCHITECTURE

The key novelty of the MultiNetEmotion model lies in its multi-scale feature extraction and fusion approach. By combining the strengths of ResNet's general feature extraction with VGG16 specific image capture capabilities, the model is able to capture a wider range of facial features. The feature fusion step and the use of a custom CNN for classification provide a novel way to leverage existing models in ensemble form for emotion detection, improving both the accuracy and generalizability of the model. This architecture ensures that the model can accurately detect subtle emotional cues, making it well-suited for real-time emotion detection in online learning systems, where understanding student emotions can help adjust pedagogical strategies dynamically.

SUMMARY OF ACHIEVEMENTS

This researched achieved its aim and objective, by successfully developing a novel MultiNetEmotion model, using convolutional neural network (CNN) framework, which is designed to extract and analyze facial features.

The model is composed of multiple layers, including convolutional, pooling, activation (ReLU), and fully connected layers, which work together to detect emotions from facial images.

The dataset was sourced from Kaggle, which include diverse set of facial expressions to ensure comprehensive emotion recognition. The dataset was organized into training and testing sets, with a detailed description of the preprocessing techniques applied to maintain consistency and reduce computational complexity. We also described the model training process, including the optimization algorithms, and loss functions. Transfer learning techniques were employed to enhance the model's generalization capabilities. The experimentation setup, including the configuration of the training environment, the hyperparameters, and the procedures for validating the model's accuracy and robustness.

The MultiNetEmotion framework was extensively evaluated, focusing on both the training and testing stages of the model. Initially, the model's architecture and parameter configuration were explored, highlighting the significant steps taken to optimize performance. Various hyperparameters such as batch size, learning rate, and dropout rate were tuned to ensure optimal training outcomes. The evaluation metrics, including accuracy, loss, precision, recall, and F1-score, were presented, showcasing the effectiveness of the model in classifying emotions across six categories: Angry, Fear, Happy, Neutral, Sad, and Surprise. The model's training performance improved over the epochs, but signs of overfitting emerged as the validation loss increased despite improving training accuracy.

Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis of the confusion matrix revealed the model's strengths and weaknesses in classifying different emotions, with the best performance observed in recognizing Happy and Surprise emotions and the most challenges with Fear and Sad. The validation accuracy reached 60%, which, while promising, indicates room for improvement.

Finally, the deployment of the model to monitor students' emotions in real-time, offering personalized content recommendations based on the detected emotional states, would enhance the user experience and facilitate a supportive learning environment by addressing negative emotions.

CONCLUSION

This researched achieved its aim and objective, by successfully developing a novel MultiNetEmotion model, using convolutional neural network (CNN) framework, which is designed to extract and analyze facial features. The model is composed of multiple layers, including convolutional, pooling, activation (ReLU), and fully connected layers, which work together to detect emotions from facial images.

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A MultiNetEmotion model, a multi-stage deep learning framework that leverages the strengths of multiple Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to detect and classify human emotions from facial expressions. The model's novelty lies in the fusion of well-established CNN architectures ResNet, VGGFace2, and a custom-built CNN for feature extraction, followed by a final CNN stage

RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT

The next step in this research will be to compare the possibilities of having improved accuracy with various combinations of machine learning models. Furthermore, we noticed overfitting that led to fluctuations in the accuracy and recommend more training time and more data to improve accuracy.

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